

Kinetic investigations on the reduction of azo dyes in absence and presence of micelle forming surfactants

S. Radjarejesri^{a,b} and N. C. Sarada^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sona College of Technology, Salem-636 005, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : uma.seshayer@gmail.com

^bChemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : ncsarada@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S by sodium sulphite was studied in the absence and presence of micelle forming surfactants, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS). The kinetic studies on the reduction of the dyes in a buffer medium of pH 7.0 revealed that the reaction is first order with respect to the dye and sulphite ion concentrations. Significant rate constant has been derived. A suitable mechanism consistent with the experimental findings has been proposed. CTAB showed inhibitory effect on the reduction of both the dyes and SDS showed no effect. This may be due to dye in the aqueous bulk phase and sulphite ions in the micellar core.

Keywords : CTAB, kinetic studies, SDS, Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S.

Introduction

Study of dye-surfactant interactions has been a subject of intense research activity due to the extensive use of these systems in analytical determinations¹. They have been employed to develop new spectrophotometric and fluorometric methods for determining micro amounts of metal ions, anions, biological compounds, drugs and pesticides^{2,3}. Amphiphilic properties of surfactants have attracted growing attention for their use in biological and chemical research applications especially in the dyeing process where the role of surfactants is very important⁴.

Analytical applications of azo dyes are well known^{5,6}. The reduction of azo benzenes to hydroxyl benzenes constitutes a convenient route to the latter's synthesis⁷. The reduction is brought about by using hydrazine⁸, titanous chloride⁹, lithium aluminium hydride, etc.^{10,11} reducing agents.

Kinetics of reduction of inorganic compounds by sulphite ions has been extensively studied¹², but comparatively less attention has been focused on the reduction of organic compounds by sulphite ions.

With a view to understand the nature and mechanism of micellar effects on the reduction reactions and to explore the utility of micellar media in controlling the rate of reduction of azo dyes, we have undertaken studies on the kinetics of reduction of aromatic azo compounds in micellar systems. As azo dyes are harmful, studies concerning facile methods of their reduction to less harmful hydrazo assumed importance.

The kinetic studies on the reduction of a series of azo dyes was studied by Ogawa *et al.* and found that SnCl₂ reduces the compounds to amine directly while Na₂SO₃ reduces them to hydrazo derivatives initially which gradually get converted to the corresponding amines¹³. As azo dyes are harmful, studies concerning facile methods of their reduction to less harmful hydrazo assumed importance.

In this part of the paper our results on the kinetics of reduction of the azo dyes by SO₃²⁻ in the absence and presence of micelles of different charge type are presented. The surfactants used for the reduction reaction are cationic surfactant (CTAB) and anionic surfactant (SDS).

Materials and methods :

Ponceau-4R, Ponceau-S, sodium sulphite, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, disodium hydrogen phosphate, acetic acid and sodium acetate were of analytical reagent grade. Sodium sulphite solution was prepared using boiled water and standardized against iodine just before use¹⁴.

The reaction was initiated by adding the requisite quantity of sodium sulphite solution to a solution containing azo compounds and other reagents. Reaction was followed spectrophotometrically using Shimadzu 160A UV-Visible recording spectrophotometer by observing the decrease in absorbance of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S at their λ_{max} 510 nm and 518 nm respectively as a function of time. At these wavelengths there is no interference on the absorption by other reagents or by the reduction products. Sodium chloride was used to determine the added salt effect. Temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at room temperature.

Results

Micellar effects on the reduction of the azo dyes by SO_3^{2-} were investigated by employing cationic surfactant CTAB and anionic surfactant SDS. Unless mentioned otherwise, studies were carried out in phosphate buffer of pH 7.0 at 298 K. Kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping the concentration of SO_3^{2-} much greater than that of dye concentration. The reduction product has been identified as a hydrazo derivative.

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S in absence of surfactants :

Effect of substrate, SO_3^{2-} , pH and added Cl^- concentrations on the reduction of Ponceau-4R :

To study the effect of Ponceau-4R, its concentration was varied in the range of 0.5×10^{-4} to 1.5×10^{-4} M keeping the $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ constant at 2.0×10^{-2} M. Plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be linear with correlation coefficients greater than 0.99, indicating the first order nature of the reaction with respect to Ponceau-4R. Data of variation of rate constant with substrate concentration is given in Table 1. Effect of $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ was studied in the range of 0.5×10^{-2} to 3.5×10^{-2} M and keeping the concentration of the substrate constant at 0.5×10^{-4} M.

The data of rate constant with SO_3^{2-} concentration is given in the Table 2. Increase in SO_3^{2-} concentration increased the rate linearly (Fig. 1), suggesting that the reaction is also first order with respect to SO_3^{2-} concentration. Effect of pH on the reaction was studied by varying the pH in the range 4.0 to 10.0. Variation of the rate constant with pH is graphically shown in Fig. 2. The rate of the reaction increased up to 7.0 and then decreased. Effect of added NaCl was studied by varying its concentration in the range 0.05 to 0.35 M (Table 1).

Effect of substrate, SO_3^{2-} , pH and added Cl^- concentrations on the reduction of Ponceau-S :

The kinetic study of reduction of Ponceau-S by sul-

Table 1. Effect of Ponceau-4R, SO_3^{2-} , Cl^- concentrations and pH on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-4R by SO_3^{2-} at room temperature

$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ pH 7.0		$[\text{Ponceau-4R}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ pH 7.0		$[\text{Ponceau-4R}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ pH 7.0		$[\text{Ponceau-4R}] = 0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ pH	
$[\text{Ponceau-4R}] \times 10^4 (M)$	$k \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$	$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \times 10^2 (M)$	$k \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$	$[\text{Cl}^-] \times 10^2 (M)$	$k \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$	pH	$k \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$
0.5	7.5	0.5	1.34	0.5	8.95	4.1	0.56
0.7	6.7	1.0	2.47	1.0	8.8	5.2	1.30
0.9	7.3	1.5	4.22	1.5	9.0	6.4	2.0
1.0	7.2	2.0	5.56	2.0	9.1	7.0	2.56
1.2	7.0	2.5	6.7	2.5	9.2	8.03	1.89
1.4	7.1	3.0	7.9	3.0	9.0	9.23	1.50
1.5	6.9	3.5	8.8	3.5	9.1	10.1	1.12
				4.0	9.3		

Table 2. Effect of Ponceau-S, SO_3^{2-} and Cl^- concentrations and pH on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by SO_3^{2-} at room temperature

 [Ponceau-S] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} M$ and pH = 7.0

$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} M$ pH 7.0		[Ponceau-S] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ pH 7.0		[Ponceau-S] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} M$ pH 7.0		[Ponceau-S] = $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}] = 2 \times 10^{-2} M$	
[Ponceau-S] $\times 10^4 (M)$	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ $\times 10^1 (M)$	$k \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})	$[\text{Cl}^-]$ $\times 10^1 (M)$	$k \times 10^3$ (s^{-1})	pH	$k \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})
0.7	0.925	0.2	2.5	0.5	0.96	3.3	1.82
0.9	0.922	0.5	3.4	1.0	1.1	4.0	2.19
1.0	1.15	0.7	4.6	1.5	0.83	5.4	2.24
1.1	0.945	0.9	5.7	2.0	1.21	7.0	3.55
1.3	0.962	1.0	6.3	2.5	1.6	8.0	1.75
1.5	0.899	1.3	8.5	3.0	1.5	10.4	1.24
1.7	1.33	1.5	10.1	3.5	1.54	11.1	0.835
1.9	1.02	1.7	11.6				
2.0	0.961	1.9	13.5				
		2.0	14.5				

Fig. 1. Variation of rate constant with $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ for the reduction of Ponceau-4R by sulphite ions.

phite ion, in the absence of surfactant is not found in the literature. Hence this attempt was made in the absence of surfactant is a work which is newly introduced. Effect of Ponceau-S concentration on the rate of reduction was studied by varying the [Ponceau-S] between 0.7×10^{-4} to $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and keeping the $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ constant at $0.2 M$. Plots of log (absorbance) versus time was found to be linear with correlation coefficients greater than 0.99, indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to Ponceau-S (Fig. 3).

Effect of $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ on the rate was studied in the range of 0.5×10^{-1} to $2.0 \times 10^{-1} M$. Data on the effect of Ponceau-S and SO_3^{2-} concentrations on the rate of the reaction is listed in Table 2. Increase of SO_3^{2-} concentration increased the rate linearly (Fig. 4), suggesting that the reaction is also first order with respect to SO_3^{2-} concentration.

Effect of pH on the reaction was studied by varying the pH in the range 3.3–11.1. Fig. 5 shows the variation

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-4R by sulphite ions.

Fig. 3. Pseudo-first order plots for the reduction of Ponceau-S representing the effect of Ponceau-S concentration.

of the rate constant with pH, graphically. There is an increase in the pH of the reaction up to 7.0 and then a decrease. Effect of added NaCl was studied by varying its concentration in the range 0.5×10^{-1} to 3.5×10^{-1} M (Table 2). Plot of added [NaCl] against rate constant is shown in the Fig. 6. Increase in the [NaCl] has negligible effect on the rate.

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S in presence of surfactants :

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R in presence of CTAB and SDS :

Effect of anionic micelle forming surfactant sodium dodecyl sulphite (SDS) and cationic micelle forming surfactant cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) on the

Fig. 4. Variation of rate constant with $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ concentration for the reduction of Ponceau-S by sulphite ions.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by sulphite ions.

rate of reduction of Ponceau-4R by SO_3^{2-} has been investigated. Studies were carried out by varying the CTAB and SDS concentration in the range 3×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-3} M (Table 3) and keeping the [Ponceau-4R] and $[\text{SO}_3^{2-}]$ constant. CTAB inhibited the reduction of Ponceau-4R (monoazo dye), using sodium sulphite. This may be due to bulkier dye in the aqueous bulk phase and sulphite ions

in the micellar core. In the case of SDS the reaction was the same as in the aqueous medium. This shows that SDS had no effect on the reaction because both the dye and sulphite ions are in the aqueous bulk phase.

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-S in presence of CTAB and SDS :

The kinetic effect of CTAB and SDS on the reduction

Fig. 6. Effect of added [NaCl] on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by sulphite ions.

Table 3. Effect of surfactants on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-4R by SO₃²⁻ at room temperature

[Ponceau-4R] = 0.5 × 10⁻⁴ M; [SO₃²⁻] = 2 × 10⁻² M and pH 7.0

Surfactant × 10 ³ (M)	k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	
	CTAB	SDS
0	6.7	6.7
0.3	6.17	6.5
0.5	5.96	6.2
0.7	4.56	6.4
1.0	No reaction	-

Table 4. Effect of surfactants on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by SO₃²⁻ at room temperature

[Ponceau-S] = 1 × 10⁻⁴ M; [SO₃²⁻] = 2 × 10⁻² M and pH 7.0

Surfactant × 10 ³ (M)	k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	
	CTAB	SDS
0	1.45	1.45
1	0.99	1.44
5	No reaction	1.45

of Ponceau-S by SO₃²⁻ was studied by varying their concentration in the range 1 × 10⁻⁵ to 1 × 10⁻² M (Table 4). Cationic micelles of CTAB exhibited very small inhibitory effect on the reactions. Anionic micelles of SDS showed no effect and the reaction was the same as in the aqueous medium in the absence of surfactants.

Discussion

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S in absence of surfactants :

Effect of varying dye concentration and SO₃²⁻ concentration revealed that the reaction is first order with respect to each of the reactants. The observed rate law under the experimental conditions for the other three dyes may be given as follows :

$$\frac{-d[S^-]}{dt} = k_1 [S^-] [SO_3^{2-}] \quad (1)$$

On the basis of the observed results the following reaction mechanism can be proposed for the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S by SO₃²⁻.

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 mentioned above leads to the mechanism

similar to the one reported earlier¹⁵ and the following equation was obtained which explains the rate dependence on H^+ concentration. Rate decrease with increase in the H^+ concentration till pH 7.0 indicates that the reaction proceeds predominantly through the path involving S^- in this pH range (Scheme 1).

$$k'_1 = \frac{k_1 + k_2 K_P [H^+]}{1 + K_P [H^+]}$$

Kinetic studies on the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S in presence of surfactants :

Effect of CTAB and SDS on the reduction of Ponceau-4R :

$1 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentration of CTAB inhibited the reaction. Catalytic and inhibitory effects of micelles can be interpreted on the basis of the mechanism and the possible interactions between the reacting species and micelles of different charge type. Cationic micelles of CTAB have inhibitory effect on the rate of reduction of [Ponceau-4R]. This effect may be due to the binding of SO_3^{2-} to CTAB micelles. In this case electrostatic forces favor binding. But approach of dye to the micellar core is expected to be prevented by electrostatic repulsions may be due to presence of bulkier group of $-SO_3H$ groups.

Inhibitory effect must be due to the shielding of these groups from the attack of SO_3^{2-} . The observed rate in the presence of CTAB may be due to the fraction of the reaction taking place in aqueous bulk phase. The inhibitory effects can also be analysed by Menger and Portnoy model¹⁶, but the effects are too small for any quantitative analysis. As the concentration of CTAB increases; more SH binds to the cationic micelles. This results in the reaction path involving SH contribution least to the overall rate. Consequently inhibition of the reaction takes place.

Anionic surfactant SDS has no effect on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-4R. This is probably due to unfavorable electrostatic interactions between dye, SO_3^{2-} and surfactant, which render the reaction to take place in the aqueous bulk phase.

Effect of CTAB on the reduction of Ponceau-S :

Effect of cationic micelles on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by SO_3^{2-} was studied by varying the CTAB concentration. At very low concentrations of CTAB, there

is no effect and at reasonably higher concentrations there is an inhibition in the reaction. A cationic micelle should catalyze anion-molecule reaction by bringing both reactants together in the Stern layer and it should inhibit a cation-molecule reaction by attracting the molecular reactant and repelling the cationic reactant.

Thus the overall effect of the micelles on the reaction rate will in general depend on both, the distribution of the reactants between the micelles and bulk solvent and the rate constants in the two environments. In the case of Ponceau-S, since the substrate has many groups of sulphite ions, the surfactant is not able to bring the reactant into the Stern layer and also there is a repulsion of the cationic reactant. Hence it is clear that the substrate and the reducing agent both are in the bulk solvent and not attracted by the surfactant. The reason most probably can be due to the two azo groups present in this compound and also the presence of bulkier sulphonate groups causing steric effects. Consequently inhibition of the reaction takes place.

Effect of SDS on the reduction of Ponceau-S :

Effect of anionic surfactant on the rate of reduction of Ponceau-S by SO_3^{2-} was investigated by varying the SDS concentration. It was found that the incorporation of anionic micelles into the reaction system showed neither rate enhancement nor inhibition. This is probably due to unfavorable electrostatic interactions between dye anion (S^-) and SO_3^{2-} which render the reaction to take place in the aqueous bulk phase. Hence the rate of the reaction is the same as in the aqueous phase in the absence of surfactant.

Conclusion

From the results of the investigations presented in this paper, it is clear that the addition of micelle forming surfactants leads to considerable rate enhancements and inhibitions of electron transfer reactions involving azo compounds. CTAB inhibited the reduction of Ponceau-4R and Ponceau-S using sodium sulphite. This may be due to dye in the aqueous bulk phase and sulphite ions in the micellar core. Anionic surfactant, SDS had no effect on the redox reactions of the dyes because both dye and sulphite ions are in the aqueous bulk phase. These findings lead to the conclusion that the nature and extent of

micellar effects on the reduction reactions of the compounds containing azo groups depends on electrostatic characters of the reacting species. The reaction proceeds with appreciable rate in absence of surfactants for both the dyes studied.

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